

ABOUT A MAXIMIN OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM FOR ONE CLASS CONTROLLABLE DIFFERENTIAL INCLUSION

Otakulov Salim¹, Abduvokhidov Fazliddin Rahmatullayevich²

¹Doctor of physical and mathematical Sciences, Professor
University of Innovation Technologies, Samarkand city,

²Senior teacher of the chair of natural science disciplines, Chirchik Higher Tank Command
Engineering Military School, Chirchik, Uzbekistan

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Annotation. In this paper the one class of controllable differential inclusions with parameter is considered. For this model of dynamic control systems under conditions of indeterminacy the optimal control problem in maximin type is researched. Using the methods of set valued analysis, theory of differential inclusions and convex analysis, in this problem considered the necessary and sufficient conditions of optimality is obtained.

Keywords: differential inclusion, control system, uncertainty parameter, maximin problem, optimal control, conditions of optimality.

1. INTRODUCTION

Deterministic models do not meet the modern requirements for effective management of complex technological and economic processes, for which errors and inaccuracies of the determining process parameters are significant. To describe the dynamics of processes without the help of probabilistic characteristics of the model's uncertainties, one can use differential inclusions [1,2]

$$\frac{dx}{dt} \in F(t, x), \quad (1)$$

where x is a phase vector from the Euclidean n -dimensional space R^n , t is time, $F(t, x)$ is a given multi-valued mapping. Differential inclusions have wide applications in the theory of optimal control, in differential games and mathematical economics. To date, the scope of research devoted to differential inclusions and their applications has significantly expanded. The theory of differential inclusions develops in various directions. We study differential-functional and integro-differential inclusions, differential inclusions with delays, partial differential inclusions, differential inclusions with a fuzzy right-hand side, and other classes of differential inclusions [3–9].

The problems for differential inclusions are of interest from the point of view of their practical application to the problems of various classes of control systems. For control systems in conditions of uncertainty, the tasks of controlling an ensemble of trajectories are of great importance. They lead to similar problems for differential inclusions to control parameters. The problems of controlling an ensemble of trajectories for control systems under conditions of uncertainty and differential inclusions are considered in [10–16]. Questions of analysis and synthesis of control systems lead to the need to study models taking into account the influence of various internal and external parameters. The class of such models includes differential inclusions with control parameters and uncertainty.

2. OBJECT OF RESEARCH AND METHODS

Consider the model of the control system in the form of differential inclusion

$$\dot{x} \in A(t)x + B(t,u) + D(t,q), \quad x(t_0) \in X_0, u \in U, q \in Q, t \in T = [t_0, t_1], \quad (2)$$

where x – n -dimensional state vector, u – m -dimensional control vector, q – k -dimensional vector of external influences, $A(t)$ – $n \times n$ -matrix, $B(t,u) \subset R^n$, $D(t,q) \subset R^n$, $X_0 \subset R^n$, $V \subset R^m$, $Q \subset R^k$. With respect to parameter q , we will assume that it is constant over the interval $T = [t_0, t_1]$, but only its set of possible values Q is known.

The control system (2) will be studied under the following assumptions:

1) the elements of matrix $A(t)$ are summable on $T = [t_0, t_1]$; 2) $X_0 \subset R^n$, $V \subset R^m$, $Q \subset R^k$ are convex compacts; 3) for any $t \in T = [t_0, t_1]$, $u \in U, q \in Q$ the sets $B(t,u)$ and $D(t,q)$ are compacts of R^n ; 4) the multi-valued map $(t,u) \rightarrow B(t,u)$ is measurable in $t \in T = [t_0, t_1]$, continuous in $u \in U$, and there is a summable function $\beta(t)$, $t \in T = [t_0, t_1]$, such that $\sup\{\|b\| : b \in B(t,u)\} \leq \beta(t)$, $(t,u) \in T \times U$; 5) the multi-valued map $(t,q) \rightarrow D(t,q)$ is measurable in $t \in T = [t_0, t_1]$, continuous in $q \in Q$, and there is a summable function $\gamma(t)$, $t \in T = [t_0, t_1]$, such that $\sup\{\|d\| : d \in D(t,q)\} \leq \gamma(t)$, $(t,q) \in T \times Q$.

By admissible controls for system (2), we mean measurable bounded m -vector functions $u = u(t)$, $t \in T = [t_0, t_1]$, which take almost everywhere on $T = [t_0, t_1]$ values from the convex compact U .

An admissible trajectory corresponding to control $u = u(t)$, $t \in T = [t_0, t_1]$, and parameter $q \in Q$ is an absolutely continuous n -vector function $x(t) = x(t,u,q)$ that satisfies almost everywhere on $T = [t_0, t_1]$ the differential inclusion (2) and the initial condition $x(t_0) \in X_0$.

We also use the following sets: U_T is the set of all admissible controls; $H_T(u,q)$ is the set of admissibly trajectories corresponding to the pair $(u,q) \in U_T \times Q$; $X_T(t,u,q) = \{\xi \in R^n : \xi = x(t), x(\cdot) \in H_T(u,q)\}$. Using the methods of work [20], we can study the convexity and compactness properties of sets $H_T(u,q)$ and $X_T(t,u,q)$, as well as the continuity, closure, and convexity of multi-valued maps: $(u,q) \rightarrow H_T(u,q)$, $(t,u,q) \rightarrow X_T(t,u,q)$.

By denoting by $X_{T_1}(u,q) = X_T(t_1,u,q)$ the set of all such points of the state space that can be reached at moment t_1 , moving along the admissible trajectories of $x(\cdot) \in H_T(u,q)$. We consider the control problem this terminal state $X_{T_1}(u,q)$ by evaluating the quality of the control process using the following non-smooth functionality:

$$I(u,q) = \inf\left\{\sum_{i=1}^l \max_{z_i \in Z_i} (z_i, P\xi) : \xi \in X_{T_1}(u,q)\right\}, \quad (3)$$

where P – $s \times n$ is a matrix, $Z_i, i = \overline{1,l}$, are compacts of space R^s . Given that in the system (2), parameter $q \in Q$ has the character of uncertainty, the terminal state $X_{T_1}(u,q)$ will be controlled according to the maximin principle (according to the principle of obtaining a guaranteed result). So, the following maximin problem we have

$$\inf_{q \in Q} I(u, q) \rightarrow \max, u \in U_T. \quad (4)$$

The control $u^* \in U_T$, minimizing a non-smooth functionality of the form

$$J(u) = \inf_{q \in Q} I(u, q) \quad (5)$$

we call optimal control in problem (4). We will study the necessary and sufficient conditions optimality in non-smooth optimal control problem (4).

Let $F(t, \tau)$ be the fundamental matrix of solutions to equation $\dot{x} = A(t)x$, $F(\tau, \tau) = E$. According to the results of the theory of differential inclusions the set $X_{T_1}(u, q)$ has the representation:

$$X_{T_1}(u, q) = F(t_1, t_0)X_0 + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} F(t_1, t)[B(t, u(t)) + D(t, q)]dt. \quad (6)$$

Let $\sigma(Y, \psi) = \inf_{y \in Y} \sigma(y, \psi)$, where $Y \subset R^n$ is bounded set. Using formula (6) and the properties of the integral of multi-valued maps, we obtain that the set $X_{T_1}(u, q)$ is a convex compact of R^n at $(u, q) \in U_T \times Q$ and the formula is true

$$\sigma(X_{T_1}(u, q), \psi) = \sigma(F(t_1, t_0)X_0, \psi) + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \sigma(F(t_1, t)[B(t, u(t)) + D(t, q)], \psi)dt. \quad (7)$$

Since

$$\sum_{i=1}^l \max_{z_i \in Z_i} (z_i, P\xi) = \max_{z_i \in Z_i, i=1, l} (P\xi, \sum_{i=1}^l z_i) = \max_{z \in coZ} (P\xi, z) = \max_{z \in coZ} (\xi, P'z),$$

then, using the formula (7) and the minimax theorem from convex analysis, we obtain that for the functional (3) the formula is valid

$$I(u, q) = \max_{z \in coZ} \left\{ \sigma(F(t_1, t_0)X_0, P'z) + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \sigma(F(t_1, t)[B(t, u(t)) + D(t, q)], P'z)dt \right\}, \quad (8)$$

where $z = \sum_{i=1}^l z_i$, $Z = \sum_{i=1}^l Z_i$, coZ is the convex hull of the set Z .

3. MAIN RESULTS

In the future, we will assume that, along with the conditions 1) – 5), the condition is satisfied: 6) the function $\sigma(D(t, q), \psi)$ is convex in $q \in Q$.

Using (5), (7), and (8), we have:

$$J(u) = \inf_{q \in Q} \max_{z \in coZ} \eta(u, q, z), \quad (9)$$

where

$$\eta(u, q, z) = \sigma(X_0, \psi(t_0, z)) + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \sigma(B(t, u(t)) + D(t, q), \psi(t, z))dt,$$

$\psi(t, z)$ – absolutely continuous solution of system $\dot{\psi} = A'(t)\psi$, $\psi(t_1) = P'z$. Functional $\eta(u, q, z)$ is convex in $q \in Q$ and concave in $z \in coZ$. Therefore, applying the minimax theorem mentioned above, we obtain the following formula from (9):

$$J(u) = \max_{z \in coZ} \left[\sigma(X_0, \psi(t_0, z)) + \min_{q \in Q} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} C(B(t, u(t)) + D(t, q), \psi(t, z))dt \right]. \quad (10)$$

Let's introduce the following functionals:

$$\mu(u, z) = \sigma(X_0, \psi(t_0, z)) + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \sigma(B(t, u(t)), \psi(t, z)) dt + \min_{q \in Q} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} C(D(t, q), \psi(t, z)) dt, \quad (11)$$

$$\rho(q, z) = \sigma(X_0, \psi(t_0, z)) + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \max_{u \in U} \sigma(B(t, u), \psi(t, z)) dt + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \sigma(D(t, q), \psi(t, z)) dt. \quad (12)$$

Theorem 1. Let: 1) $u^*(t), t \in T = [t_0, t_1]$, – optimal control in the problem (4);

2) $z^* \in coZ$ – point of the global maximum of the function $z \rightarrow \mu(u^*, z)$.

Then for almost all $t \in T = [t_0, t_1]$ the equality holds

$$\max_{u \in U} \sigma(B(t, u), \psi(t, z^*)) = \sigma(B(t, u^*(t)), \psi(t, z^*)). \quad (13)$$

Proof. Since $u^*(t), t \in T = [t_0, t_1]$, is the optimal control in problem (6), then

$J(u^*) \leq J(u), \forall u \in U$, where $J(u)$ has the form (5). Therefore, using (10) and (11), we have:

$$\max_{z \in coZ} \mu(u^*, z) \geq \max_{z \in coZ} \mu(u, z), \quad \forall u \in U_T. \quad (14)$$

Let $z^* \in coZ$ be an point of the global maximum of function $z \rightarrow \mu(u^*, z)$. Then from (14) we get

$$\int_{t_0}^{t_1} \sigma(B(t, u^*(t)), \psi(t, z^*)) dt \geq \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \sigma(B(t, u(t)), \psi(t, z^*)) dt, \quad \forall u \in U_T.$$

Therefore,

$$\int_{t_0}^{t_1} \sigma(B(t, u^*(t)), \psi(t, z^*)) dt \geq \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \max_{u \in U} \sigma(B(t, u), \psi(t, z^*)) dt.$$

From here we get

$$\int_{t_0}^{t_1} \sigma(B(t, u^*(t)), \psi(t, z^*)) dt = \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \max_{u \in U} \sigma(B(t, u), \psi(t, z^*)) dt. \quad (15)$$

Due to the properties of the Lebesgue integral, it follows from (15) that equality (13) holds for almost all $t \in T = [t_0, t_1]$.

Let us use the result of the proved theorem. First, given (5) and (10), we have :

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{z \in coZ} [\sigma(X_0, \psi(t_0, z)) + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \max_{u \in U} \sigma(B(t, u), \psi(t, z)) dt + \min_{q \in Q} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \sigma(D(t, q), \psi(t, z)) dt] = \\ & = \max_{u \in U_T} \max_{z \in coZ} [\sigma(X_0, \psi(t_0, z)) + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} C(B(t, u(t)), \psi(t, z)) dt + \min_{q \in Q} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} C(D(t, q), \psi(t, z)) dt] = \\ & = \max_{u \in U_T} \min_{q \in Q} I(u, q). \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Next, let $u^*(t), t \in T = [t_0, t_1]$ be the optimal control in problem (4), and $z^* \in coZ$ be the point of the global maximum of function $z \rightarrow \mu(u^*, z)$. Then, using (5), (10), (11), (13), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{u \in U_T} \min_{q \in Q} I(u, q) = \max_{u \in U_T} \max_{z \in coZ} \mu(u, z) = \max_{z \in coZ} \mu(u^*, z) = \mu(u^*, z^*) = \\ & = \sigma(X_0, \psi(t_0, z^*)) + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \sigma(B(t, u^*(t)), \psi(t, z^*)) dt + \min_{q \in Q} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \sigma(D(t, q), \psi(t, z^*)) dt = \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sigma(X_0, \psi(t_0, z^*)) + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \max_{u \in U} \sigma(B(t, u), \psi(t, z^*)) dt + \min_{q \in Q} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \sigma(D(t, q), \psi(t, z^*)) dt \leq \\
 &\leq \max_{z \in coZ} [C(X_0, \psi(t_0, z)) + \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \max_{u \in U} C(B(t, v), \psi(t, z)) dt + \min_{q \in Q} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \sigma(D(t, q), \psi(t, z)) dt]. \quad (17)
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, taking into account the definition (14) of the functional $\rho(q, z)$, from (16) and (17) we get that z^* is the point of the global maximum of the function $z \rightarrow \min_{q \in Q} \rho(q, z)$. Therefore, the following necessary optimality conditions are valid.

Theorem 2. Let $u^*(t), t \in T = [t_0, t_1]$, be the optimal control in problem (4). Then there exists a $z^* \in coZ$ – point of the global minimum of the function $z \rightarrow \min_{q \in Q} \rho(q, z)$ by coZ , such that, for almost all $t \in T = [t_0, t_1]$, equality (13) holds.

4. CONCLUSION

The necessary optimality condition for the considered non-smooth maximin type problem is given in Theorem 1 in the form of relation (13). It should be noted that in the case where $(t, u) \rightarrow B(t, u)$ is a single-valued mapping, condition (13) takes the form well known from the Pontryagin maximum principle [2]. Theorem 2 complements and clarifies results of theorem 1. In conclusion, we note that in the work developing the research methods [16], the results are obtained, which are the theoretical basis for the development of an algorithm for constructing optimal control in the considered maximin problem.

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